

Table S1. Proteins targeted by DAPI, Acridine orange, and Ethidium bromide, nominated with SWISSTARGET prediction, with the corresponding probabilities.

Ligand	Targeted protein	Common name	Uniprot ID	Target Class	Probability
DAPI	Quinone reductase 2	NQO2	P16083	Enzyme	0.098
	S-100 protein β chain	S100B	P04271	Cytosolic protein	0.098
	Plasma kallikrein	KLKB1	P03952	Protease	0.098
	Urokinase-type plasminogen activator	PLAU	P00749	Protease	0.098
	Coagulation factor VII	F7	P08709	Protease	0.098
	Histamine H4 receptor	HRH4	Q9H3N8	Family A GPCR	0.098
	Serine protease hepsin	HPN	P05981	Protease	0.098
	Thrombin and coagulation factor X	F10	P00742	Protease	0.098
	Thrombin	F2	P00734	Protease	0.098
	Coagulation factor IX	F9	P00740	Protease	0.098
	Androgen Receptor	AR	P10275	Nuclear receptor	0.098
	Cyclin-dependent kinase 5/CDK5 activator 1	CDK5R1 CDK5	Q15078 Q00535	Kinase	0.098
	Dual-specificity tyrosine-phosphorylation regulated kinase 1A	DYRK1A	Q13627	Kinase	0.098
Acridine Orange	Beta amyloid A4 protein	APP	P05067	Membrane receptor	0.223
	Telomerase reverse transcriptase	TERT	O14746	Enzyme	0.117
	Serotonin 3a (5-HT3a) receptor	HTR3A	P46098	Ligand-gated ion channel	0.109
	Serotonin 1a (5-HT1a) receptor	HTR1A	P08908	Family A GPCR	0.100
	Bcl-2-related protein A1	BCL2A1	Q16548	Unclassified	0.101
	Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1	EGFR	P00533	Kinase	0.101
	Adrenergic receptor beta	ADRB2	P07550	Family A GPCR	0.101
	Alpha-1d adrenergic receptor	ADRA1D	P25100	Family A GPCR	0.101
	Alpha-1a adrenergic receptor	ADRA1A	P35348	Family A GPCR	0.101
	Alpha-1b adrenergic receptor	ADRA1B	P35368	Family A GPCR	0.101
	Fatty acid desaturase 1	FADS1	O60427	Enzyme	0.101
Ethidium bromide	Telomerase reverse transcriptase	TERT	O14746	Enzyme	0.815
	Acetylcholinesterase	ACHE	P22303	Hydrolase	0.105
	Carbonic anhydrase VI	CA6	P23280	Lyase	0.105
	Carbonic anhydrase VB	CA5B	Q9Y2D0	Lyase	0.105
	Carbonic anhydrase VA	CA5A	P35218	Lyase	0.105
	Carbonic anhydrase XIII	CA13	Q8N1Q1	Lyase	0.105
	Amiloride-sensitive cation channel 3	ASIC3	Q9UHC3	Ligand-gated ion channel	0.105

Fig. S1. Classes of proteins targeted by DAPI (A), Acridine orange (B), and Ethidium bromide (C) predicted by SWISSTarget prediction.